

A Study on Recruitment Process in “Midland Microfinance Limited” at Jal

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ABSTRACT

Human Resources is the most valued and most treasured asset for any Organization. Best Outcome can be Judged with the efficient Recruitment and Selection strategies. The main objective of this paper is to streamline Recruitment process in Midland Microfinance Ltd at Jal. The study also focuses its attention to carry out and promote a fair and transparent recruitment procedure. The well-structured questionnaire was used for the data collection. The source of data was both primary and secondary. Data analysis has been done with statistical tools like tables, graphs, bar diagrams etc. With reference of to this context the research paper entitled Recruitment has been prepared to put light on Recruitment process. The main objective of the study is to Highlights on the most preferable method for recruitment, as well as To study various the sources used for recruitment in Midland microfinance limited company in Jalandhar.

Keywords-- Recruitment, Employees, Organization, Management

I. INTRODUCTION

Recruitment facilitates to identify and encouraging prospective employees to apply for a job. The recruitment process differs from one organization to others. Employee referrals, transfers promotions, retirements, walk-in , internal advertisements are the internal recruitment sources used by many organizations. But in modern scenario, with the entry of social media recruitment process was drastically changed. Methods like Online Recruitment or E-Recruitment are mostly used by many organizations for attracting the prospective employees, but Midland micro finance ltd is prefer using traditional methods.

Company Profile

Midland Microfin Limited provides financial services. Savings, business loan, insurance, credit, money transfers, counseling, etc is offered by Company. and other financial support services. It also serves customers in all over India. Mission of the company is to encourage micro enterprises as source of sustainable livelihood, by providing financial services with the help of technology.

II. OBJECTIVES

1. To analyze the most preferable method for recruitment.

2. To study various the sources used for recruitment.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

Olatunji and ugoji (2013) in a study of personnel recruitment on organizational development: a survey of selected Nigerian workplace using primary data to study certain recruitment procedures adopted in organizations and revealed that the recruitment procedures used in the organization influence personnel behaviour and performance though the study did not use any variable to measure organizational development or performance rather it measures the perception of male and female toward recruitment.

Mustapha et.l (2013) opined that the aim of recruitment goes beyond mere filling of vacancies to include individual development and achievement and building a strong organization where effective team work and the individual's needs are realized at the same time.

Flora (2014) argued that merit and demerit of the use of recruitment agencies to a firm is the same thing with that of external recruitment sources which he listed be: qualified personnel, a wider choice of candidates, fresh talent, competitive spirit among candidate etc.

Compton, Morrissey, Nankervis 2014, says Getting recruitment and selection processes and techniques right the first time is crucial and is the product of human resource planning, job design, human resource development, remuneration systems, career and succession plans to satisfy and motivate qualified applicants (Compton, Morrissey, Nankervis 2014).

Ntiamoah et al., p. 4, 2014 say that recruitment and selection have become ever more important as organizations increasingly regard their workforce as a source of competitive advantage.

Adeyemi, Dumade and Fadare (2015) in the study of the influence of recruitment and selection on organizational performance using questionnaire to study a sample of only twenty respondents of Access Bank branch. The study indicated that, advertising of job vacancies to general public, use of employment agent(s), the study also show that employee referrals are mostly the mode for recruiting potential employees, it was also realized that the method used in the recruiting and selection process was very effective.

Ekwoaba, Ikeije, and Ufoma (2015) in a study of the impact of recruitment and selection criteria on

organizational performance revealed that recruitment and selection criteria have a significant effect on organization's performance that the more objective the recruitment and selection criteria, the better the organization's performance.

used in this study. Primary as well as the secondary sources was used for collection of data. Primary data is in the form of Questionnaire, observation, Telephonic Interview and secondary data involves the Books, Journals, newspaper and other research report.

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Methodology is a method to solve the research problem systematically Descriptive Research is

Sample Size

Sample was carried out at Midland Microfinance Limited.

Statistical Tools Applied: - Are Bar diagram, Pie etc.

Data Analysis and Interpretations
Analysis About Most Preferable Method Followed by Company

Response	Number Of Respondents	% of Respondaents
Direct Method	74	74%
Indirect Method	14	14%
Third Party	8	8%
Others	4	4%
Total	100	100%

Interpretation

From the above table /graph it is observed that 74 Respondents have accepted that company is following Direct Method for Recruitment and 14 Respondents are in

favour of Indirect Method as well as 8 Respondents prefers Third Party and 4 Respondents come in the category of Others.

Analysis about the Kind of Recruitment Sources were used by the Organization:

Response	No. of Respondents	% of Respondents
Present Permanent Employee	8	8%
Present Temporary Employee	12	12%
Retired Employee	16	16%
Disabled Employee	14	14%
All Above	50	50%
Total	100	100%

Inference

From the above graph ,it is clear that company prefers the Present Employee, Temporary employees, Retired employee, Disabled employee as internal source for Recruitment.

V. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

- The study was confined to the Recruitment of the employees of Midland Micro Finance pvt ltd Jal.
- Collecting data properly from employees become difficulty due to the time constraint.
- Busy schedule of the employees also effected to some extent.
- There is a chance for bias in the information given by the respondents.
- HR department does not want to disclose the whole information.

VI. CONCLUSION

In every organization Recruitment plays a vital role. The study reveals that 74% respondents prefer, direct method for recruitment, as well as elucidate the various sources used for recruitment.

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